

COMMUNITY PROBLEMS: ITS INFLUENCE ON THE QUALITY OF LIFE OF THE RESIDENCE OF BARANGAY BANGAS IN HADJI PANGLIMA TAHIL, SULU

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ABSTRACT

The study used descriptive quantitative approach to describe the respondents' community problems and its influence on the quality of life at Barangay Bangas in Hadji Panglima Tahil, Salu using checklist questionnaire constructed and developed by the researchers, tested its reliability using split half method at Cronbach's Alpha .677 for part 1 and .823 for part 2 and Correlation Values between forms .755, purposive sampling research design selecting 50 respondents. Mean and regression were also used. The study revealed the following significant findings. The respondents moderately agree that there are problems that can affect the quality of life of Bangas residents. These problems are lack of water supplies, electricity, motivation from the authority to promote hard work, training in fishing and seaweeds farming and competition of seaweeds farming, LGUs support, cooperative and organizations, public transportation and fishing facilities. The residents of Barangay Bangas agree that they have quality of life, although their livelihood is not comparable to the quality standard of living. The quality of life they have is reasonably suited for their conditions as the living in the rural setting; the hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is significant influence of the problems of the Barangay Bangas residents on the quality of their lives. It implies that when the problems of the Barangay Bangas could be addressed and given appropriate solutions there is greater probability of improving the quality of their lives. The study concluded that the problems of Barangay Bangas residents such as lack of water supplies, electricity, motivation from the authority to promote hard work training in fishing and seaweeds farming and competition of seaweeds farming, LGUs support, cooperative and organizations, public transportation and fishing facilities have positive influence on their quality of lives, when the problems of the Barangay Bangas residents could be addressed and given appropriate solutions there

is greater probability of improving the quality of their lives. The following recommendations are forwarded. The LGUs may provide assistance to the residents of Barangay Bangas. The residents may be organized into cooperatives or associations. The residents may be given orientation to motivate them to have self-reliance and may be granted assistance by the BARMM government for their livelihood projects. The residents may be given due attention to improve their livelihood.

Keywords: *Community Development, Quality of Life, Rural Livelihood Challenges*

INTRODUCTION

Since the time, the island of Barangay Bangas in Hadji Panglima Tahil, Sulu became barangay, the residents already live in misery and poverty. The barangay has the smallest share land area with a total of 284.7 hectares, which is only around 58% of 4,950 hectares total land area of the municipality. It is also evident that the changes in the environment have diversely affected the livelihood activities and has been considered as one of the causes of poor seaweed harvest and decreasing fish catch. The presence of commercial fishing and dynamite fishing within the municipal water is so much affecting the income of the fisher folks.

It is important to create strategic plan so that the environment is protected in order to maintain the ecological balance and help sustain livelihood activities especially fishing and aquaculture activities. These activities can promote sufficient livelihood to refrain from poverty. Poverty is the lack of the basic needs of life, including food, shelter, clothing, and safe drinking water. For a person to live normally, it is important to meet a certain level of physical, social, and emotional needs. People who live in poverty have difficult time to achieve those as they are not allowed to catch fish and plant seaweeds and other activities in many places. Because of their low income, they encountered troubles in maintaining their health, hunger, and education of their children. Although, poverty has become a large issue around the world, but it is something that many of us know about and were not realizing just how large a problem it is for many people who live on few resources, like very few incomes in a day.

Due to poverty the lifestyle of most people here in the island who are depending only on the seaweed farming, gill net, fish cage and other marine culture activities will affect the education and the future of their children. Seaweeds farming is the common livelihood in the barangay, when not sustained, they remain in poverty. Consequently, seaweeds farming has great advantage among other economic activities in the island. Everyone including woman can do the task of farming. This study will investigate the problems that influence the lifestyles of the residents in Barangay Bangas in Hadji Panglima Tahil municipality in the province of Sulu.

Research Questions

This study sought to answers of the following research questions.

1. What are the community problems that affects the quality of life of the residents of barangay Bangas in Hadji Panglima Tahil, Sulu?
2. What is the quality of life of the residents of Barangay Bangas in Hadji Panglima Tahil-Sulu?
3. Is there significant influence of the community problems and the quality of life of the residents of Barangay Bangas in Hadji Panglima Tahil, Sulu?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study made use of quantitative approach with descriptive analysis research design. It is being used to describe the study accurate way about the respondents in the Community Problems its influence on the quality of life of the residents of Barangay Bangas in Hadji Panglima Tahil, Sulu (Talikan, 2021; Talikan et al., 2024).

Research Locale

The research study was conducted in Barangay Bangas, Hadji Panglima Tahil, Sulu, is situated approximately 6, 1134, 120. 9666 in the island of Sulu. Elevation of these coordinates is estimated at 3.5 meter or 11.5 feet above mean sea level with latest population of Bangas grew from 1,752 in 1990 to 2,052 in 2020, an increase of 300 people over the course of 30 years. The latest of 0.59%, or an increase of 57 people, from the previous population of 1,995 in 2015.

Barangay Bangas, Hadji Panglima Tahil, Sulu, is one of the islands of Sulu, separated from the Jolo proper, 18.8km distance from the municipality of Hadji Panglima Tahil. The municipality has a land area of 67.90 square kilometers on 26.22 square miles which constitutes 1.49% of Sulu total area. Hadji Panglima Tahil via car ferry or boats bound for Panglima Tahil can be found at Jolo fish market. The ride will take just about an hour.

Research Instrument

The instrument used to acquire primary data in this study is checklist questionnaire personally prepared by the researchers. It was launched personally by the researchers in Barangay Bangas, Hadji Panglima Tahil, Sulu. The study was conducted on the year 2022-2023. The questionnaire has two parts. The first part inquires the profile of the respondents, and second part inquires the community problems they encountered in life and struggles to achieve the best quality of life. The following scales will be used in the questionnaire. 1-Strongly Disagree (SDA); 2-Disagree (DA); 3-Moderately Agree (MA), 4-

Agree (A), 5-Strongly Agree (SA).

Validity and Reliability

A questionnaire was constructed and developed by the researcher with the help of the subject instructor and was used as a tool for gathering data. The questionnaire is composed of inquiries of the profile and perceptions on the community problems of the residents in their lives. The questionnaire was validated by professors of course Community Development. Its reliability was tested using split half method. Split half method is characterized by dividing the questionnaire into halves then identifying the Cronbach's Alpha and Correlation values between forms. The Cronbach's alpha greater than .667 and .823 and the correlation between forms .755 indicates reliable questions.

Sampling Design

This study used purposive sampling research design. Purposive sampling design based on the objectives of the study. The study utilized the residents of Bangas to determine the perception on the Community Problems in life.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of this study are composed of 25 male and 25 female residents of Bangas, Hadji Panglima Tahil, Sulu.

Data Gathering Procedures

To collect the data, the researchers sent a letter to the Barangay Official from the Barangay Bangas in Hadji Panglima Tahil, Sulu. The researchers launched the questionnaire delivering house to house.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The researchers used Statistics Package for Social Science (SPSS) in the computation of data, with the help of their instructor. To answer problems 1 and 2, weighted arithmetic mean was used. To answer problem number 3 simple regression was used.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Problems that Affect the Quality of Life of the Residents of Barangay Bangas

Table 1.1 shows that the residents of Barangay Bangas have some problems. The respondents agree that they lack water facilities, electricity, motivation from the authority, and training in fishing and seaweeds farming. They are also involved in competition of seaweeds farming.

The residents of Barangay Bangas moderately agree that they lack support from the LGUs, space for farming seaweeds, cooperative and other organizations, public transportation and fishing facilities.

The problems of the residents in any place can affect the quality of their lives. These problems cannot be solved by the individual residents alone, but with the strong support of the government. However, the residents of Barangay Bangas have agreed that their problems are lack of water supplies, electricity, motivation, training in fishing and seaweeds farming and involved in farming competition. These problems have affected the quality of their lives as water supplies and electricity are the basic needs of every family. Training for fishing and seaweeds farming are the means of their livelihood which they are also practicing the competition in seaweeds farming that can create hatred in their hearts. Many studies in psychology have revealed when the heart is not clean there will be no peace of mind. The teaching in Islam, the Messenger Muhammad (SAW) have said "there is a parcel of meat in your body; if this parcel is good your body will be good, if this parcel will be bad your body will be bad; Indeed, this parcel is the heart (Rawahu Muslim).

The peaceful and enlightened community is the one that is equipped with proper lighting facilities, water supplies, and enough occupation to maintain their livelihood. Indeed, the people of Barangay Bangas is confronted with basic problems that the government may come to rescue them in order to feel the beauty of life in this world.

To help them maneuver such problems, related literature has suggested that before confronting community problems, it is important to understand how social workers can construct conceptions of social workers and community problems intervention. We seek analytic tools that can make clear the nature of a problem and its potential relationships to its environment and solutions. However, the construction is not just, or even primarily, an analytic exercise. The construction of a social problem definition for community practice must begin with the involvement of the affected community groups. (Shwartz-Ziv & Strier, 2020). This involvement begins to counter the effects of social exclusion, increase community empowerment, allows the community to take greater control over conditions of their lives, and begins the intervention process (Mayo, 2004; Turin et al., 2021).

Hence to address the problems of Barangay Bangas, it may involve some constructive arrangement with the social workers, LGUs, and the residents, being the subject of the initiative.

The overall mean indicates that the respondents moderately agree that there are problems than can affect the quality of life of Bangas residents. These community problems are lack of water supplies, electricity, motivation from the authority to promote hard work, training in fishing and seaweeds farming and competition of seaweeds farming, LGUs support, cooperative and organizations, public transportation and fishing facilities.

Table 1.1. Problems that affect the Quality of Life of Bangas Residents

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
Lack of water facilities to improve basic needs of the residents.	2.02	.140	Agree
Lack of electricity to operate machines industry	2.02	.140	Agree
Lack of motivation from the authority to promote hard work	2.22	.503	Agree
Competition for seaweeds farming decreases income of the residents	2.41	.753	Agree
Lack of training in fishing and seaweeds farming	2.43	.728	Agree
Lack of support from LGUs, thus, the constituents have insufficient livelihood facilities	2.82	.994	Mo Agree
Through community problems like lack of space for seaweeds farming, the livelihood is difficult	2.86	.664	Mo Agree
Lack of cooperative and other organization devoid of government projects	2.92	.688	Mo Agree
Lack of public transportation to deliver goods to market and vice versa	3.06	.506	Mo Agree
Lack of fishing facilities to improve livelihood	3.18	.994	Mo Agree
N = 51; Overall Mean	2.59	.611	Mo Agree

Legend: 4.5.0-5.0(1) = Strongly Disagree; 3.5-4.49(2) = Disagree; 2.5-3.49(3) = Moderately Agree; 1.5-2.49(4) = Agree; 1.0-1.49(5) = Strongly Agree

Quality of Life of the Residents of Barangay Bangas

Table 1.2 shows that the respondents strongly agree that they have 4Ps livelihood program and have enough income from fishing and seaweeds farming enough to sustain the needs of the family and savings.

The respondents agree that they have small area for seaweeds farming but the income is not enough to support the family needs, have small business capable to support the family needs, have enough income for the needs of the family, owned a banca for fishing but income is not enough to sustain the needs of the family, and working in the LGU Barangay level, but the salary is not enough to sustain the needs of the family.

The respondents moderately agree that they have monthly income but not enough to sustain the needs of the family, the family living is dependent on 4Ps program, have regular 4Ps benefits and little income to maintain the needs of the family, and have sari-sari store for livelihood.

The overall mean indicates that the residents of Barangay Bangas agree that they have quality of life, although their livelihood is not comparable to the quality standard of living. The quality of life they have is reasonably suited for their conditions as they are living in the rural setting.

Table 1.2. Quality of Life of the Residents of Barangay Bangas

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
I have no 4Ps Livelihood Program. I have enough income from fishing and seaweeds farming enough to sustain the needs of my family and our savings	1.47	.612	Strongly Agree
I have small area for seaweeds farming but the income is not enough to support the needs of my family	1.73	.568	Agree
I have small business and I am capable to support the needs of my family	2.24	.438	Agree
I have enough income for the needs of my family	2.24	.681	Agree
I have banca for fishing, but my income cannot sustain the needs of my family	2.31	.735	Agree
I am working in LGU Barangay Level, and my salary is enough to sustain the needs of my family	2.35	.483	Agree
My monthly income is not enough for my family	2.59	.829	Mo Agree
My family living is dependent on 4Ps Program	2.63	.774	Mo Agree
My family receive 4Ps Livelihood Program regularly and I have little income from my fishing enough to sustain the needs of my family	2.65	1.055	Mo Agree
I have sari-sari store whose income is enough to support the needs of my family	2.69	.990	Mo Agree
N = 51; Overall Mean	2.29	.7155	Agree

Legend: 4.5.0-5.0(1) = Strongly Disagree; 3.5-4.49(2) = Disagree; 2.5-3.49(3) = Moderately Agree; 1.5-2.49(4) = Agree; 1.0-1.49(5) = Strongly Agree

Influence of Problems on the Quality of Life

Table 1.3 shows that the Regression value indicates strong influence of problems on the quality of life of Bangas residents. In fact, the Regression Square values indicates that 82.5 percent of the data are accounted by the Regression model. The F values with significant value lesser than .05 significance indicates that the hypothesis is rejected, therefore, there is significant influence of the identified problems of Barangay Bangas residents on their quality of life. The Beta Coefficient values with t-values have sig2-tailed values lesser than .01 indicates that the problems of the Barangay Bangas residents are good predictor of their quality of lives.

The data indicates that the hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is significant influence of the problems of the Barangay Bangas residents on the quality of their lives.

The data implies that when the problems of the Barangay Bangas could be addressed and given appropriate solutions there is greater probability of improving the quality of their lives. This means when they are given water facilities, electricity, enough space for seaweeds farming, fishing facilities, given strong support and motivation by the LGUs, etc., there will be very good quality of their lives. Otherwise, without completion of

these problems they will remain as the quality of lives they are in today.

Based on this finding, Kapur (2019) states that it is necessary for the LGUS, social workers, educators, and other members to pay adequate attention towards bringing about improvements in the quality and efficiency of education. With advancements taking place and with the advent of globalization and modernization, it is necessary to improve quality of life (Guliyeva, 2021). Improving quality of life would enable the individuals to satisfactorily achieve progress and development and enhance the standing of livelihood institutions within the community. Furthermore, the LGUs, social workers and educators will incur the feeling of job satisfaction, develop motivation towards the implementation of their job duties and feel pleasurable within the working environment. Furthermore, residents would also feel pleasurable and develop interest and enthusiasm towards enriching their quality of lives by performing their task in the community involvement. The main areas that have been taken into account in this research paper are, strategies implemented by LGUs, social workers and teachers to improve quality life, additional ways to enhance quality and efficiency of the system of education, and improving quality and efficiency of education through effective administration.

Brauer et al. (2014) emphasized that contemporary transformations of rural areas involve changes in land uses, economic perspectives, connectivity, livelihoods, but also in lifestyles, whereupon a traditional view of "the rural" and, consequently, of 'rural development' no longer holds. Accordingly, EU's 2007-2013 Rural Development Policy (RDP) is one framework to incorporate aspects labelled as quality of life (QOL) alongside traditional rural tenets. With a new rendition of the RDP underway, the extent of the expired RDP regarding its incorporation of QOL, in order to better identify considerations for future policy making.

Antonan, et. al., (2018) states that the concept of the quality of life and tries to explain its peculiarities in the rural space considering different levels of education, professional activities, mobility, ways of dwelling, access to the social and technical infrastructure. The subjective perception of the rural quality of life can be manifested in moving in and moving out. The main shortages of the rural quality of life can be seen (by rural people) in a poor access to the prestigious and well-paid jobs and to a richer social life. The main advantages of the rural way of life are generally evaluated (by urban people) by better access to the nature. A promotion of the local identity is considered as an important tool for improving the rural quality of life (besides of a solution of infrastructural problems), considering the enormous difference among rural areas of a big differentiation of the countryside.

Brahmakshatriya (2020) states that rural development involves efforts that are economic and social in nature intended to encourage concepts of retention, growth, and expansion in areas outside cities, including improving quality of life for rural residents through such activity.

Table 1.3 Influence of Problems of Bangas Residents on their Quality of Life

Model	Unstandardized B Coefficients	Standardized Beta Coefficients	T	Sig.	R-square
1 (Constant)	.050		.136	.895	.825
POR	.863	.908	6.131	.000	

Dependent Variable: QOLR

Findings

The study used of descriptive quantitative approach to describe the respondents' community problems its influence on the quality of life at Barangay Bangas in Hadji Panglima Tahil, Sulu using checklist questionnaire constructed and developed by the researchers tested its reliability using split half method at Cronbach's Alpha 677 for part 1 and 823 for part 2 and Correlation Values between forms 755. Purposive sampling research design selecting 50 respondents. Mean and regression were used.

The study revealed the following significant findings:

1. The respondents moderately agree that there are problems that can affect the quality of life of Bangas residents. These problems are lack of water supplies, electricity, motivation from the authority to promote hard work, training in fishing and seaweeds farming and competition of seaweeds farming. LGUs support, cooperative and organizations, public transportation, and fishing facilities.
2. The residents of Barangay Bangas agree that they have quality of life, although their livelihood is not comparable to the quality standard of living. The quality of life they have is reasonably suited for their conditions as they are living in the rural setting.
3. The hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is significant influence of the problems of the Barangay Bangas residents on the quality of their lives. It implies that when the problems of the Barangay Bangas could be addressed and given appropriate solutions there is greater probability of improving the quality of their lives.

Conclusions

The problems of Barangay residents such as lack of water supplies, electricity, motivation from the promote hard work, training in fishing and seaweeds farming and competition of seaweeds farming, LGUs support, cooperative, and organizations, public transportation, and fishing facilities have positive influence on their quality of lives when the problems of the Barangay Bangas residents could be addressed and given appropriate solutions there is greater probability of improving the quality of their lives.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are formulated.

1. The LGUs may provide assistance to the residents of Barangay Bangas.
2. The residents may be organized into cooperatives or associations.
3. The residents may be given orientation to motivate them to have self-reliance.
4. The residents may be granted assistance by BARMM government for their livelihood projects.
5. The residents may give due attention to improve their livelihood.

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